

How Do Adverse Childhood Experiences Affect The Likelihood Of Engaging In Criminal Activity?

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ABSTRACT

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) consist of various stressful childhood experiences that affect a child's future mental well-being and behaviour. This research paper examines how adverse childhood experiences affect the likelihood of engaging in criminal activity. An extensive literature review was conducted that explores the link between ACEs and criminal behaviour, as well as causal factors and preventive measures of ACEs. The findings reveal that there is a positive correlation between the presence and number of ACEs and criminal activity. The paper aims to highlight the effect of various factors, more specifically, environmental factors and stigmatization, on ACEs, and how ACEs can affect emotion regulation, behavioural development, and neurological development, which in turn influences behaviour. Preventative and intervention measures of ACEs, such as psychotherapy and drug therapy, are further underscored to show how the likelihood of engaging in criminal activity can be decreased.

Keywords: Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs), Emotion regulation, Mental health, Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), Stigmatization, Protective factors

Introduction

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are usually defined as the stressful experiences that affect a child as a result of their upbringing (McManus, 2018), and could impact their psychological health in the long term (Scott, 2020). A few examples of ACEs are: Physical and emotional abuse, neglect, household instability etc., which includes living with relatives with mental illnesses, having incarcerated parents or relatives, or having parents who were once victims of ACEs, having relatives involved with substance abuse or divorced parents. These can all affect a child's upbringing. (What Are ACEs? And How Do They Relate to Toxic Stress?, 2024; Luspe, 2019) and may contribute to criminal behaviours in the future. Numerous studies have shown that ACEs are linked to detrimental effects, such as aggressive behaviour, in adulthood that later results in criminal activities. For instance, Reavis et al. (2013) investigated ACEs and adult criminality, in which offenders completed an ACE questionnaire, and found that they had about four times as many ACEs than non-offenders. Therefore, ACEs have shown to have a positive relationship with criminal behaviour.

The prevalence of ACEs has been shown to increase with increasing factors, such as low socio-economic status, mental health problems etc. For instance, Madigan et al. (2023) investigated the global prevalence of ACEs and its meta-analysis has shown that at least 60.1% of adults have experienced one or more ACEs, in which one of six adults reported exposure to four or more ACEs prior to age of 18. There was also strong evidence to show that higher prevalence of ACEs was found in those with a history of mental health, addiction to substances, and low socio-economic status.

Understanding the relationship between ACEs and criminal behaviour is essential in developing protective factors for children to ensure that they grow up in a safe environment, as short or long term exposure to ACEs and letting this trauma go untreated, increases the likelihood of health and social problems in the future (Webster, 2022). Therefore, this paper aims to demonstrate the link between ACEs experienced and the likelihood of criminal activity by individuals through examining the psychological and behavioural impacts of ACEs, for example, emotion regulation, behavioural and neurological development in victims of ACEs, and how protective factors, such as environmental factors, preventative and intervention measures, can reduce the impacts and occurrence of ACEs, and as a result, decrease criminal activity.

Link between ACEs and Crime

There are multiple research studies that support the link between ACEs and Crime, and highly encourages the need for intervention of these behaviours (Reavis et al., 2013; Bauer et al., 2024; Basto-Pereira et al., 2022; Yohros, 2023; Edalati et al., 2017; Ashekun et al., 2023). For instance, Reavis et al. (2013) analysed and supported the link between ACEs and criminal behaviour in adults, in which this showed a correlation between ACEs and negative health effects as they explored maladaptive behaviors and crime populations. The findings have shown that criminal behavior is associated with childhood adversity as there is a positive relationship between the number of ACEs and negative behaviors developed in criminals compared to non-offenders. Reavis et al. (2013) has further suggested that methods to intervene ACEs should be addressed to reduce the number of underlying traumas stemming from early adverse experiences.

Bauer et al. (2024) expands on how specific ACEs, their relationship with one another and the context of the incidence affects their impact on criminal behaviour. The findings revealed when certain ACEs are experienced together, they may result in different types of criminal behaviour, such as violent or non-violent crimes. Bauer et al. (2024) also showed the effect of cumulative ACEs, where although there is a positive relationship between cumulative ACEs and crime, certain types of ACEs are revealed to have a stronger effect on the type of crime. In conclusion, there was an increase in the likelihood of crime as the number of ACEs increases, and some ACEs are strongly linked to one another, further demonstrating how ACEs will have a cumulative effect on crime.

Basto-Pereira et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between ACEs and criminal behavior in young adults across several countries and continents, highlighting how interconnected ACEs are while reducing the likelihood of culture bias in their findings. From the cross-national sample, ACEs were shown to be predictors of criminal behaviors across various countries, thus reinforcing the idea of intercultural relationships between ACEs and criminal outcomes

Individuals with ACEs in vulnerable positions are shown to have a higher prevalence of negative outcomes. Edalati et al. (2017) investigates the impact of ACEs on the likelihood of criminal behavior with a sample of homeless adults with mental illnesses, in which the

findings support how ACEs are overrepresented in these populations, thus highlighting the disproportionate effect of ACEs on these individuals. The findings also suggest how the environment increases one's vulnerability in engaging in dangerous behaviors, leading to developing maladaptive behaviours. Thus, this study demonstrates how the history of ACEs increases the risk of criminal activity.

In conclusion, different factors have been shown to stimulate the development of ACEs in these researches, and how ACEs have affected one's behavior, thereby leading them to engage in criminal behavior and commit crimes.

Impact of environmental factors on ACEs

Family dynamics and one's social environment has the ability to influences the likelihood of ACEs, which can result in criminal behaviour. Victims of ACEs tend to eventually exhibit and display those adverse behaviours, thus resulting in a generational cycle (McManus, 2018). This can be explained through observational learning, referring to learning by watching, imitating and exhibiting actions of others. Humans actively seek out and take in information from one's surroundings, according to Social Cognitive Theory, which holds that people are active information processors (Gallagher, 2012). They can learn new knowledge, abilities, and behaviours via this process and change them to fit their own needs.

Bandura et al. (1961) investigated the concept of observational learning, in which children would imitate the behaviour of their role models, the adults. The results revealed that children exposed to aggressive behaviour were able to reenact the same actions as the adult aggressor just by observation. In other words, the children were able to remember this behaviour and reproduce it when encouraged to do so. Ybarra et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between violent media in childhood and aggressive behaviour during. By examining the impact of violent content across different media types, they established a significant positive correlation between one's exposure to violent media and violent behaviour as they grow. Liu and Xu (2023) further specifically demonstrate how childhood exposure to domestic violence results in the increase in violent crime in adulthood. By using the Social Learning Theory and Cognitive Theory (Gallagher, 2012), they argued that witnessing domestic violence brings on profound long-lasting negative impacts on a child's physical, cognitive, social and emotional development, which can lead to an increased likelihood of engaging in violent behaviour later in life, creating a generational cycle of violence. Due to the normalisation of physical

punishments, more than half of children around the world have increased vulnerability to learning violent behaviour. According to the Social Learning Theory, children witnessing these violent behaviours learn that it is a justifiable way of behaving to control others. They observe and learn how violence can lead to desired outcomes and thus imitate that behaviour, which could lead to the development of maladaptive beliefs. They may internalise the idea that violence is an acceptable and considered an effective way to solve problems. This can then lead to an increase in violent criminal behaviour in the future. Thus, this study concludes that violence experienced as a child will have significant impacts on one's cognitive development. Violent behaviours can be learned as a child, and in certain conditions, manifest, thereby creating the cycle of generational ACE. However, not all children behave that way, and it is important to note that stigmatising and ostracising all children that are related to criminals may lead to greater detrimental effects.

Impact of stigmatization on ACEs

As victims of ACEs are looked down upon by society, thus increases the likelihood of criminal activity coming from the victims. Stigmatization is defined as the act of describing or considering somebody or something in a way that unfairly suggests that they are bad or do not deserve respect (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries.). According to Goffman (1963), stigma can be deemed as having a 'spoiled identity'. Social Stigma is one of the most common 'levels' of stigma. It is the belief that is followed by a large faction of society and any irregular individuals, such as those with mental conditions or behavioural disorders, are considered part of an inferior group (Dudley J. R., 2000). This, therefore, may enable inequality and disparities between individuals, such as access to clinical and health service, and thus, could be the beginning of increased criminal behaviour due to the lack of help and support (Ahmedani, 2011).

Stigmatising those that underwent ACEs could also be due to a lack of awareness of the topic. "Only about 20 percent of U.S. adults know about ACEs." The epidemiologist leading the Number Story project, Sarah Marikos, had said (Morgan, 2021). Thus, individuals that suffer from the actions of ACE victims label them as "unstable" and "criminals." This generates negative reactions from both sides, where ACE victims become more unwilling to seek help and support to hide their trauma, which in turn increases the likelihood of criminal behaviour and harm.

The preconception of individuals with mental problems stemming from ACEs influences how others view them, which in turn, affects how they interact, help or provide opportunities for. Furthermore, the belief that criminals due to ACEs would have a harder time to adjust to society after their sentence can lead to a decline in their mental wellbeing and the development of maladaptive behaviours which increases the difficulty of returning to normal society. Moore et al. (2016) investigated the relationship between behaviour of criminals due to ACEs after release from prison and preconceived stigma of their behaviour. The findings revealed that due to these beliefs, criminals released from incarceration have a harder time adjusting back to society (Moore et al., 2016). Thus, it is likely that the recidivism rates of these criminals are higher, in accordance to what society thinks of them (Yohros, 2023).

Pager (2003) also supports the argument that criminals have to climb higher hurdles to assimilate back into society when exploring the traces of criminal records. It was found that individuals with the mark of a criminal, despite having equivalent qualifications to other applicants, had significantly lower rates of callbacks, revealing the barriers to securing employment due to discrimination. This underscores how criminal records influence the employability of criminals, thus demonstrating how stigmatization increases the impact of ACEs on individuals.

Impact of ACEs on emotion regulation and behavioural development

ACEs have been shown to affect the regulation of emotion, and in turn, one's behaviour, as the relationship between ACEs and psychological distress appears to have a positive trend (Cole & Diaz, 2024). Rudenstine et al. (2019) investigated how emotional regulation relates to ACEs, and found a direct link between ACEs and adult psychological stress, with the lack of emotion regulation significantly affecting one's stress level, and in turn, their behaviour.

Furthermore, regulating emotions is important in working out criminal behaviour, as it may affect one's ability to think and make decisions. Emotions condenses information so we are able to respond quickly, however, it also influences the decisions we make and thereby affect the conclusions made in short amounts of time, and thus decreases the accuracy and reliability of the decisions we make (Polo et al., 2024).

Moreover, ACEs can affect an individual's behaviour and personality traits, making them more susceptible to committing crimes. As mentioned, social cognitive functioning and

aggressive behaviour are affected by ACEs. Emotion regulation had an effect in decisions that encourage maladaptive behaviour, which are known as cognitive distortions, such as all-or-nothing thinking, over-generalization, magnification and arbitrary inferences (Rnic et al., 2016; Garnefski et al., 2004) in which are comparable to criminal behaviours. The relationship between regulating emotions, criminal thinking and maladaptive behaviour was investigated in a cross-sectional study, Avila (2021), which included MTurk workers. The results revealed the likelihood of engaging in aggressive and maladaptive behaviours could be anticipated by errors in coping of emotions. Moreover, specific criminal thinking and behaviours were linked to maladaptive emotional control. Aggressive behaviours are also associated with struggles in regulating emotions, more specifically, management of impulse control, suppression and conveying of emotions (Thompson, 1991). Thus, the present body of research validates the theory that the lack of emotional control can influence cognitive processes and behaviour.

The lack of regulation of emotions can be explained by the correlation between ACEs and behaviour. As ACEs stimulate exceeding the child's ability of cope with high levels of stress (Pechtel, 2011) , and further enables cognitive vulnerability due to depressive cognitions being directly provided by the abuser (Rose et al., 1992), children's cognitive thinking will be primed negatively and cause them to be more vulnerable to depression.

Therefore, since hypothesis supports emotion regulation influencing maladaptive behaviours, the lack of emotion regulation is thus associated with risky and criminal behaviour (Álvarez-Hierro & Oliver, 2024) .The dual-processing model shows the relationship between emotion regulations and criminal behaviour, in which the brain's prefrontal cortex (PFC), mainly responsible for rational and higher order function, together with the limbic system, investigates and weights the benefits and disadvantages of past experience to regulate behaviour. Thus, in intense situations, the limbic system allocates sentimental value to various responses, thereby influencing one's mood (Exum, M. L., 2015). Heightened emotions may lead to bias (Brown & Kulik, 1977) of the recollection of memories, and since ACEs has impacted the past experiences of individuals, this increases the likelihood of engaging in criminal activity (Avila, 2021).

In conclusion, the lack of emotion regulation due to the presence of ACEs has a significant impact on an individual's behaviour, specifically criminal behaviour. By impairing the ability

to not only manage emotions, but also control behaviour due to past traumas, this results in the lack of development of the right behaviour, thereby increasing the likelihood of faulty behaviour.

Impact of ACEs on neurological development

ACEs bring trauma to the human brain, and the development of the victim's brain. Rybak et al. (2006), focuses on Frontal Alpha Power Asymmetry in aggressive children and adolescents due to trauma. This research investigates the relationship between brain activity, specifically the difference in electrical activity between the left and right frontal lobes, and aggression and disruptive behaviour disorders in children and adolescents. The findings revealed that the left frontal lobe had much lower alpha power than the right frontal lobe in those that have experienced any trauma or abuse. More recent research has shown that the left frontal activity is associated not only with positive behaviour, but also negative emotions, such as aggression and anger (Zinner et al., 2008; Harmon-Jones et al., 2010). Therefore, the findings support the idea that there is a positive correlation between the Frontal Alpha Power Asymmetry in the left frontal lobe due to past trauma and criminal behaviour.

The neurological impact of ACEs thus further contribute to mental illness, such as Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), Depression etc. (Tabb et al., 2022), and increased risk of diagnosis is associated with increased exposure of ACEs (Felitti et al., 1998). The result of one's mental health is affected by the psychological impacts of ACEs. Hypothesis that an individual's neurological development is affected by mental health disorders caused by ACEs, have been thought of by various researchers, including Müge Cantürk and Herzog J. I..

Cantürk et al (2021) conducted a study where the development of psychiatric conditions in male prisoners due to the negative experiences in their childhood was investigated. The findings demonstrated a positive relationship between violent criminal behaviour and childhood trauma through the scores of a childhood trauma questionnaire and the Violence Tendency Scale (VTS). Moreover, Herzog et al. (2018) investigated the consequence of ACEs on the neurobiological and psychosocial conditions on individuals, in which this research places ACEs to be a major stressor with long-lasting negative effects on brain development. Individuals with a history of ACEs often display amygdala hyperactivity, thus increasing vulnerability to maladaptive behaviours. This illustrates the psychological stress

that victims are subjected to, which evolves into mental disorders and trauma, such as PTSD, depression, anxiety etc.. Thus, individuals with mental issues that originate from ACEs are more likely to commit criminal behaviour (Paulino et al., 2023), in which to reduce these long-term mental health risks, early prevention and intervention to ACEs are crucial.

Prevention and Intervention Methods

Thus, to reduce the likelihood of ACEs, protective factors, such as preventative and intervention methods, have been introduced into society. Protective factors are basic factors that protect one's mental and physical health, such as education, financial stability, positive and healthy environments (O'Connell et al., 2009). One aspect of having a healthy childhood includes learning from a good role model, in which are their parents, guardians or adults in the children's surroundings, as seen in Bandura et al. (1961).

By increasing the availability of education and knowledge of ACEs to the public, this may increase the possibility of individuals taking action to positively support victims of ACEs and thereby reducing the likelihood of them engaging in criminal activity. Dr Karen Schucan Bird (Schucan et al., 2024) researched on how one's family and friends influence the victims' decision in seeking help. Her review has demonstrated that educational activities and classes created to help the victims of ACEs have significantly affected the spread of awareness and increased motivation to help ACE victims (Schucan et al., 2024).

Helping younger generations to be aware of the signs and connection between ACEs and criminal behaviour is vital, as they can play a major role in aiding victims of ACEs. These habits would be developed early and thus, will be easier in reducing ACEs. For example, safe and secure environments not only for learning, but also building connections between students and teachers in the U.S. occur through the use of CDC's Division of Adolescent and School Health (DASH). This includes mental health programmes to assist in bridging students to caring and friendly healthcare specialists, where students can receive appropriate and culture inclusive knowledge and skills to reduce ACE trauma from affecting victims in the future (Felitti et al., 1998).

Therapy aims to provide support to individuals who aim to change their mindset and live a healthier life. There are two types of commonly used therapy. Psychotherapy and Drug Therapy. Psychotherapy is a preventative and intervention method which focuses more on

addressing a person's life situation and subjective understanding of his or her psychological problems due to ACEs. Psychotherapy helps people identify unhealthy thought patterns and behaviours as well as suggests strategies to manage stress and symptoms. The two most common psychotherapies are Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and Interpersonal Therapy (IPT). Attending psychotherapy before criminal behaviour is expressed can help prevent it, as acquiring new skills or coping mechanisms, honing them through practice, and being prepared to employ them in difficult situations can help avert worsening circumstances or crises (Zhou et al., 2017). Psychotherapy to rehabilitate criminal behaviour is also a common intervention measure, and based on Beaudry et al. (2021), it can be said that psychotherapy is associated with decreased rates of recidivism.

Drug therapy, on the other hand, is a biological approach to treatment which sees maladaptive behaviour as a mental illness and refers to those who seek treatments as patients. Biomedical approaches to treatment are based on the assumption that if the problem is based on biological malfunction. It suggests that many chemicals are involved in a system responsible for the regulation of mood. Holloway et al. (2006) investigated the effectiveness of drug treatment programs on reducing criminal behaviour, and have successfully shown that the likelihood of engaging in further crimes after receiving treatment was significantly reduced among those that participated in the drug treatment programs compared to those without treatment.

These actions above can be considered preventative measures, in which risk factors are eliminated to provide a safe environment to individuals (American Psychological Association., 2014), in this case, children who have yet to show symptoms of abuse. By implementing preventative measures before criminal behaviour has developed, such as protective environments and education, the quality of life of those individuals can improve (Fusar-Poli et al., 2021). However, even though preventative measures are deemed important and useful (Benning et al., 2022), individuals that have a relapse in behaviour may require other types of intervention treatment later in life. Therefore, it is difficult to decide which preventive or intervention methods are more effective as each individual may responds to various treatments differently, thus, more in-depth research is required and should be conducted for future reference.

Conclusion

In order to examine how ACEs affect the likelihood of engaging in criminal activity, the relationship between ACEs and criminal activity was explored (Reavis et al., 2013; Bauer et al., 2024; Basto-Pereira et al., 2022; Yohros, 2023; Edalati et al., 2017; Ashekun et al., 2023). In conclusion, various factors influencing the behaviour of those surrounding the victim of ACEs, such as environmental factors and stigmatization (McManus, 2018; Gallagher, 2012; Bandura et al. 1961; Ybarra et al. 2022; Liu and Xu, 2023), can all impact ACEs, and ACEs can then affect the development of emotion regulation (Cole & Diaz, 2024; Rudenstine et al., 2019; Avila, 2021; Thompson, 1991; Pechtel, 2011; Rose et al., 1992; Álvarez-Hierro & Oliver, 2024; Exum, M. L., 2015), behaviour, and neurological state of the victim (Rybak et al., 2006; Zinner et al., 2008; Harmon-Jones et al., 2010; Tabb et al., 2022; Felitti et al., 1998; Cantürk et al., 2021; Herzog et al., 2018; Paulino et al., 2023), thus affecting their mental state. This then may lead to criminal behaviour. As the number of ACEs increases, the probability of criminal behaviour increases, according to research.

The likelihood of committing crimes depends on the effect of ACEs. Various research highlights the positive relationship between ACEs and a large number of psychological conditions, such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression etc., in which they may then result in criminal behaviour. Research by Cantürk et al. (2021) and Reavis et al. (2013) reveals a strong positive correlation between aggression and trauma, more specifically ACEs, thus suggesting that early hardship and difficulties may lead to development of maladaptive thinking and behaviour, thereby increasing the aggressive nature of the victims. The results demonstrated how lingering trauma, and the lack of emotion regulation can be developed as psychological effects of ACEs, resulting in the criminal behaviour cycle. Therefore, to reduce criminal behaviour from developing and disrupt the cycle of ACEs and criminality, it is important to treat these psychological side effects by making use of preventive and intervention methods.

Furthermore, family relationships also play an important role in determining whether ACEs encourage criminal behaviours to develop. As seen by the cycle of ACEs, experiencing trauma during their childhood increases the likelihood of imitating and replicating those same experiences and behaviours towards their own family members, thereby mirroring the adverse occurrence they had in their childhood. According to the Social Cognitive Theory and the concept of observational learning, behaviours such as violence can be learnt just by paying attention to such actions. Bandura et al. (1961) is one such research that demonstrates

how young children can easily learn violent behaviour through visual learning, thus reinforcing the cycle of ACE.

Therefore, one of the most important aspects of a better-quality life is the presence of prevention and intervention methods, such as increased education, psychotherapy and drug therapy, as they aid in the reduction of crime due to better awareness and safer environments as they tackle the root causes of the problem, thereby eliminating the issue before it occurs, and prevent the continuity of criminal activity. However, it is also important to recognise that extensive treatments can be acquired later in life for those who display severe criminal behaviours. Thus, handling and treating harmful behaviours to benefits both individuals and society is through preventative actions and immediate or later interventions (O'Connell et al., 2009; Schucan et al., 2024; Felitti et al., 1998; Zhou et al., 2017; Beaudry et al., 2021; Holloway et al., 2006; Fusar-Poli et al., 2021; Benning et al., 2022).

One future topic for research could be how prevention and intervention methods affect recidivism rates of criminals. Recidivism rates are highly relevant as they directly impact the safety and wellbeing of the public, and by developing better prevention and intervention methods, this can help reduce the likelihood of former criminals recommitting or committing new crimes, which in turn will not only lower crime rates and increase the sense of security of the public, but may also manage to break the cycle of crime (Bower et al., 2024; Lamberti, 2016; Beaudry et al., 2021; Yukhnenko et al., 2023; Fulham et al., 2023).

Limitations

It is important to take note that findings from research studies only include criminals with ACEs that have been found and reported. Those who have not been caught would not be included in the results, thus the findings may only show a small population of those that have been identified. This could be due to the fact that criminals caught have been considered more severe and more easily detectable, therefore, this research could be considered a one-sided perspective.

Moreover, it is not common for criminals to be tested for ACEs as it is not thoroughly integrated into the criminal justice system (Ford et al., 2019). This may be due to the lack of awareness and training to understand the importance of criminals with ACEs, as the criminal justice system focuses more on legal factors, such as whether one is guilty or innocent

(Lattimore, 2022), and risk in their behaviours. Therefore, ACEs are not routinely checked in criminals, affecting the data of actual number of criminals with ACEs.

Furthermore, many studies rely on self-reports, and this will affect the validity of the studies due to social desirability bias of the criminals. In addition, the term 'childhood' is vague as there are many stages of childhood, thus studies acknowledge the need for further research on the different effects of ACEs at different stages of one's childhood.

The location of the research taking its place is essential in determining the accuracy of the results as the culture of the area and its traditions affect the environment one grows up (Wartmann & Purves, 2018; Prince D., 2014). For instance, certain cultures have prejudice against criminals and thus make it harder for the criminals to be accepted back into society, and therefore, reducing the likelihood of assimilating back into a normal society (Clow et al., 2012; Strauss-Hughes et al., 2019; Smiley et al., 2016). Moreover, having mental health issues are not commonly talked about and this may hinder those that want to seek help. These traditions instilled in society may affect the behaviour towards those suffering from mental health issues, former criminals etc. (Pang et al., 2018; Tan et al., 2020; Ahad et al., 2023), and thus affect the number of people willing to admit the truth during the research.

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